

**THE STUDY OF DEVIATIONS FROM THE NORMAL DISTRIBUTION OF
SUMS OF INDEPENDENT OR DEPENDENT RANDOM VARIABLES
USING GENERAL ESTIMATES OF DIFFERENCE PSEUDO MOMENTS**

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Abstract. In this article, using the method of semi invariants under the Statulevicius condition, general uneven estimates of approximation by a normal distribution are obtained and estimates of absolute pseudo moments are obtained on the basis of this. In order to obtain similar estimates in limit theorems for sums of independent or dependent random variables, it is sufficient to obtain an estimate of semi invariants of the Statulevicius type. These results can be used in tasks related to the analysis of rare events and in statistical testing tasks, where we want to test, for example, the hypothesis that the data is distributed normally.

Keywords: Cumulants, the Statulevicius condition, uneven estimate, difference pseudo-moment, probabilities of large deviations.

Introduction.

The publication of non-classical estimates in limit theorems for sums of independent random variables began in the second half of the last century with the fundamental works of V. M. Zolotarev (see, for example, [9]). Out of the many problems, one of the most relevant issues of theoretical and practical interest was obtaining estimates using difference pseudo-metrics. Here, pseudo moments are used to compare two distributions when constructing estimates of the accuracy of the approximation of distributions. For example, such estimates in the case when one of these distributions is normal are obtained in [5].

In this paper, general non-uniform estimates of the approximation to the normal distribution and estimates of difference pseudo moments in the zones of large deviations are obtained by the method of semi invariants under the condition of Statulyavichus on the semi invariants of the random variables. In order to obtain similar estimates in the limit theorems for sums of independent or dependent random variables, it is sufficient to obtain an estimate of seven Statulevicius-type invariants.

Research methods and main results.

Consider a random variable (r.v) $\eta = \eta_{\Delta}$, depending on the parameter Δ , with a distribution function $F_{\eta}(x) = P(\eta < x)$ with mean $E\eta = 0$ and variance $D\eta = 1$.

We denote $\Gamma_k\{\eta\}$ as a seven –invariant k –of the k th order sl. in η , $\Phi(x) = P(N < x) - (0,1)$ the normal distribution, $\chi_s(\eta, N) = s \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x|^{s-1} |F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| dx$ are difference pseudo moments of order $s \geq 1$.

Suppose that there are constants $\gamma \geq 0, H > 0, \Delta > 0$ such that the Statulevicius condition is satisfied:

$$|\Gamma_k\{\eta\}| \leq H(k!)^{1+\gamma} / \Delta^{k-2}, k = 3, 4, \dots, l \tag{S_\gamma}$$

In this paper, we obtain some general estimates for the values $\chi_s(\eta, N)$ under the condition (S_γ) . The estimate for $\chi_s(\eta, N)$ is based on general non uniform estimates for the value $|F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)|$, obtained using the general lemma on the probabilities of large deviations [15], as well as on exponential estimates of the distribution r.v [14].

Lemma 1. Let sl. in η with $E\eta = 0$ and $D\eta = 1$ satisfy the condition (S_γ) . Then

1) At $0 \leq x \leq 1$

$$|F_\eta(-x) - \Phi(-x)| = |F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| \leq c(\delta, \gamma) / \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \tag{1}$$

$$c(\delta, \gamma) = \frac{2160}{\delta} \left(\frac{\sqrt{6}}{2}\right)^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \left(1 + \frac{2560}{\delta^4 e^4}\right), 0 < \delta < 1;$$

2) For $1 \leq x \leq \sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}$

$$|F_\eta(-x) - \Phi(-x)| = |F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| \leq \frac{c(\delta, \gamma) x^3 \exp\{-x^2/2\}}{\sqrt{2\pi} \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \tag{2}$$

Proof. Using the general lemma on the probabilities of large deviations [15], in the interval $1 \leq x \leq \sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}$, we can obtain the following estimate:

$$|F_\eta(-x) - \Phi(-x)| = |F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| \leq (1 - \Phi(x)) \left\{ |1 - \exp\{L_\gamma(x)\}| + |1 - \exp\{L_\gamma(x)\}| \cdot |f_j(x)| \cdot \frac{x+1}{\Delta_\gamma} + |f_j(x)| \cdot \frac{x+1}{\Delta_\gamma} \right\} \tag{3}$$

Here $L_\gamma(x) = \sum_{3 \leq i < q} \lambda_i x^i + \theta(x/\Delta_\gamma)^3, q = \{\frac{1}{\gamma} + 2, \gamma > 0 \infty, \gamma = 0, |\theta| < 1$

λ_i are expressed in terms of the semi invariants r.v in η , where

$$L_\gamma(\pm x) \leq \frac{x^3}{2(x+8\Delta_\gamma)}, \tag{4}$$

$$f_j(x) = \frac{60(1+10\Delta_\gamma^2 \exp\{1-x/\Delta_\gamma\}\sqrt{\Delta_\gamma})}{1-x/\Delta_\gamma}, j = 1, 2 \Delta_\gamma \text{ is given in } \tag{1}$$

Let then $0 \leq x \leq \sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}$. Then using (4) it is easy to check that $L_\gamma(\pm x) \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and hence

$$|1 - \exp\{L_\gamma(\pm x)\}| \leq 2|L_\gamma(\pm x)| \leq \frac{x^3}{x+8\Delta_\gamma} \tag{5}$$

Let's denote $\delta = \left(1 - 1/\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}\right)$

moreover, for sufficiently large $\Delta > 0$, it can be shown that $0 < \delta < 1$.

Further, for $0 \leq x \leq \sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}$, we obtain in an elementary way

$$|f_j(x)| \leq \frac{60}{\delta} \left(1 + \frac{2560}{\delta^4 e^4}\right), j = 1, 2 \tag{6}$$

Now let $0 \leq x \leq 1$, then using (5) and (6) from (3) we obtain (1). If $0 \leq x \leq \sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}$, meaning that

$$\Phi(-x) = 1 - \Phi(x) \leq \frac{1}{x\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\{-x^2/2\} \tag{7}$$

(see[8].page 192) using also (5) and (6) from (3), we obtain (2)

Lemma 1 is proved.

Lemma 2. Let r.v in η with $E\eta = 0$ and $D\eta = 1$ satisfy the condition (S_γ) .

Then there is a constant $c(\delta, \gamma)$, which is estimated by:

$$\chi_s(\eta, N) \leq c(\delta, \gamma) / \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \tag{8}$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_s(\eta, N) &= s|F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| dx + s|F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| dx \leq \\ &\leq s|F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| dx + sP(N \geq x) dx + sP(\eta \geq x) dx = J_1 + J_2 + J_3 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Next J_1 , we estimate by (1) and (2). J_2 by (7), J_3 and by the estimate obtained in [14]: if the condition (S_γ) is satisfied, then for all $x \geq 0$

$$P(\pm\eta \geq x) \leq \exp\{-x^2/4H\} \text{ if } 0 \leq x \leq (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}; \tag{10}$$

$$P(\pm\eta \geq x) \leq \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{4}(x\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}\right\} \text{ if } x \geq (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \tag{11}$$

Let's evaluate J_1 . Using (1) and (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &= s \int_{-1}^1 |x|^{s-1} |F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| dx + s|F_\eta(x) - \Phi(x)| \leq \frac{sc(\delta, \gamma)}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \left(\frac{2}{s} + \right. \\ &\left. \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x|^{s+2} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx\right) \leq \frac{4sc(\delta, \gamma)}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x|^{s+2} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$E|N|^m = \begin{cases} \frac{m!}{2^{m/2} \left(\frac{m}{2}\right)!}, & m - \text{is even}; \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} 2^{(m-1)/2} \left(\frac{m-1}{2}\right)!, & m - \text{is odd}. \end{cases}$$

(12)

Then taking (12) $m = s + 2$ we get

$$J_1 \leq \frac{c_i(s, \gamma)}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}}, i = 1, 2 \tag{13}$$

Where $c_i(s, \gamma) = \begin{cases} \frac{4sc(\delta, \gamma)(s+2)!}{2^{\frac{(s+2)}{2}} \left(\frac{s+2}{2}\right)!}, & s - \text{is even}, i = 1, 4 \\ c(\delta, \gamma) \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} 2^{\frac{(s+1)}{2}} \left(\frac{s+1}{2}\right)!, & \end{cases}$

$s - \text{is odd}, i = 1;$

Let's evaluate J_2 . Using (7), we obtain $J_2 \leq \frac{2s}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} x^{s-2} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx$

It is known (see page 176 in [7]) that

$$\int_a^{\infty} x^p \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx \sim a^{p-1} \exp\{-a^2/2\}, a \rightarrow \infty \tag{14}$$

Therefore

$$\int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} x^{s-2} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx \sim \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^{s-3} \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}/2\right\}$$

for sufficiently large Δ_γ , the expression

$$J_{2s}(\Delta_\gamma) = \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^{3-s} \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}/2\right\} \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} x^{s-2} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx$$

restricted.

We denote $C_{2s} = J_{2s}(\Delta_\gamma)$

Then

$$J_2 \leq \frac{2sC_{2s}}{\sqrt{2\pi}\Delta_\gamma} \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^s \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}/2\right\} \quad (15)$$

The function $M_{2s}(\Delta_\gamma) = \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^s \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}/2\right\}$ reaches its maximum at $\Delta_\gamma \geq$

1. Let's denote

$$M_{2s} = M_{2s}(\Delta_\gamma) \quad (16)$$

Given (16) from (15), we have

$$J_2 \leq \frac{2sC_{2s}M_{2s}}{\sqrt{2\pi}c_\gamma} \frac{1}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \quad (17)$$

Let us now evaluate J_3 . We use (10) and (11). Let $\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma} \leq (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{\frac{1}{(1+2\gamma)}}$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} J_3 &\leq 2s \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{(H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{\frac{1}{(1+2\gamma)}}} x^{s-1} P(\eta \geq x) dx + 2s \int_{(H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{\frac{1}{(1+2\gamma)}}}^{\infty} x^{s-1} P(\eta \geq x) dx \leq \\ &\leq 2s \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} x^{s-1} \exp\left\{\frac{-x^2}{4H}\right\} dx + 2s \int_{(H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{\frac{1}{(1+2\gamma)}}}^{\infty} x^{s-1} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{4}(x\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}\right\} dx = \\ &= J_3' + J_3'' \end{aligned}$$

To evaluate J_3' , we use (14) again. We have

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} x^{s-1} \exp\{-x^2/4H\} dx \\ &= (\sqrt{2H})^s \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^{s-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^2/2\right\} d\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right) \sim \\ &\sim (\sqrt{2H})^s \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^{s-2} \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2}/2\right\} \end{aligned}$$

Let's denote $C'_{3s} = J'_{3s}(\Delta_\gamma)$, $M'_{3s} = M'_{3s}(\Delta_\gamma)$

where

$$J'_{3s}(\Delta_\gamma) = \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^{2-s} \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2/2}\right\} \times \\ \times \int_{\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^{s-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^2/2\right\} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^{s-1} \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right)^2/2\right\} d\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2H}}\right) \\ M'_{3s}(\Delta_\gamma) = \left(\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma}\right)^{s+1} \exp\left\{-\sqrt[3]{\Delta_\gamma^2/2}\right\}$$

Then

$$J_3' \leq 2s(\sqrt{2H})^s C'_{3s}(\Delta_\gamma) M'_{3s} / c_\gamma \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \tag{18}$$

To estimate J_3'' , we use the following asymptotic relation (see[13], page 35)

$$\int_a^\infty x^{p-1} \exp\{-\beta x^\mu\} dx \sim \frac{1}{p} a^p \exp\{-\beta a^\mu\}, a \rightarrow \infty \tag{19}$$

Taking $p = s, \beta = \frac{1}{4}, a = (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}, \mu = \frac{1}{1+2\gamma}$ from (19), we have

$$J_3'' \sim \frac{2s}{\Delta^s} \frac{1}{s} (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{4} (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)^2}\right\}$$

Let's denote $C_{3s}'' = J_{3s}''(\Delta), M_{3s}'' = M_{3s}''(\Delta),$

where

$$J_3''(\Delta) = \frac{s \exp\left\{\frac{1}{4} (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)^2}\right\}}{(H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \int_{(H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}}^{\infty} (x\Delta)^{s-1} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{4} (x\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)}\right\} d(x\Delta), \\ M_3''(\Delta) = \Delta^{(1-2s\gamma)/(1+2\gamma)} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{4} (H^{1+\gamma}\Delta)^{1/(1+2\gamma)^2}\right\}$$

Then

$$J_3'' \leq 2sH^{\frac{s(1+\gamma)}{1+2\gamma}} C_{3s}'' M_{3s}'' / \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}. \tag{20}$$

As a result, from (18) and (20) we obtain

$$J_3 \leq 2s \left(\frac{(\sqrt{2H})^s}{c_\gamma} C_{3s}'' M_{3s}' + H^{\frac{s(1+\gamma)}{1+2\gamma}} C_{3s}'' M_{3s}'' \right) \frac{1}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} \tag{21}$$

Finally, using (13), (17) and (21) from (9), we obtain (8):

$$\chi_s(\eta, N) \leq \left((c_i(s, \gamma) + \frac{2sC_{2s}M_{2s}}{\sqrt{2\pi}c_\gamma} + 2s \left(\frac{(\sqrt{2H})^s}{c_\gamma} C_{3s}' M_{3s}' + H^{\frac{s(1+\gamma)}{1+2\gamma}} C_{3s}'' M_{3s}'' \right) \right) \times \\ \times \frac{1}{\Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}} = c(s, \gamma) / \Delta^{1/(1+2\gamma)}$$

Lemma 2 is proved

Consequences of general lemmas.

Let $X_t, t = 1, 2, \dots$ with $EX_t = 0$ and $DX_t = 1$ is a random process defined on $(\Omega, F, P), \{F_s^t; 1 \leq s \leq t \leq \infty\}$ -family σ - of algebras: $F_s^t \subset F, \forall s \leq t; F_{s_1}^{t_1} \subset F_{s_2}^{t_2}; \forall [s_1; t_1] \subset [s_2; t_2]; \sigma\{X_n; s \leq n \leq t\} \subset F_s^t, X_t$ satisfies the Rosenblatt condition with the α -displacement coefficient:

$$\alpha(s, t) = |P(AB) - P(A)P(B)| \quad , \quad Z_n = \frac{S_n}{B_n}, \quad S_n = \sum_{t=1}^n X_t, \quad B_n^2 = MS_n^2 > n\sigma_0, \sigma_0 > 0$$

Conclusion.

From Lemmas 1 and 2 we can obtain similar statements of theorems 1 and 2 using the statements of theorem 4.23; 4.25-4.31 in the monograph [11]. If we take into account that these estimates take place in zones of large deviations, the rough constants do not greatly affect the deviation error by n .

We can use the theorems obtained in this way, for example, in statistical testing problems, where we want to test, for example, the hypothesis that the data are normally distributed. From this we can construct control charts to test the stability of the distribution parameters when studying random processes.

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